

ADVANCES IN DIGITAL SCHOLARLY EDITING

PAPERS PRESENTED AT THE DIXIT CONFERENCES
IN THE HAGUE, COLOGNE, AND ANTWERP

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Documenting the digital edition on film¹

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Paper presented at 'Technology, Software, Standards for the Digital Scholarly Edition' DiXiT Convention, The Hague, September 14-18, 2015.

Introduction

Film is used for ethnographic data collection in the social sciences (Banks 1995) but less so as a method of disseminating research (Baptiste 2015) or documenting the creation of academic work in the arts and humanities (Bell 2006). The first two decades of the 21st century saw an explosion of online learning environments and eventually MOOCs, which often disseminate knowledge in the form of short digital films. This medium reaches wide audiences through easily accessible, sharable and usable interfaces like YouTube and Vimeo. Digital films are modular, reusable, redistributable, and with a growing market of low-cost equipment, can be scaled up or down to fit many different project budgets and levels of expertise. Given this potential, the short academic film can be viewed as a complimentary method to document the creation of digital editions and explain their technical and intellectual content.

Documentation as a necessary part of academic output

In the hard sciences, replicating the results of a proof or experiment is a way of validating those results. Replication necessitates an accurate description of the steps taken to form the results in question. This is made geographically complex in the

1 This brief presentation was given as part of the panel 'Editing and Society: Cultural considerations for construction, dissemination and preservation of editions.' Rather than presenting research results on a finished experiment, it is intended to provoke conversation about one aspect of a forthcoming project on scholarly filmmaking in the digital humanities.

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digital scholarly editing community, where collaborative networks spread out over countries or even continents is the norm, and the considerable task of documenting meetings, building websites, metadata and mark-up choices may be distributed unevenly throughout the (often multi-year) lifecycle of a digital edition. And though digital scholars may apply previously developed tools, theories or editing styles to their projects, innovation rather than replication is the goal. Nevertheless, there has been a significant uptick in digital project collaborators documenting their editorial practice through conference presentations and in user guides on edition websites. Documentation can significantly affect how a digital resource is used and reused (Warwick *et al.* 2009). If users have difficulty understanding where to start with a digital resource, they may simply choose to exit. Conversely, creating textual and audio-visual guides with detailed descriptions of the technical and academic content therein can be a good way of increasing users' time on the website, and could potentially increase engagement with its materials.

Understanding the technical infrastructure and theoretical underpinnings that lead to the creation of a digital edition also can engender a sense of appreciation for its value as a scholarly/art object (Bell 2006). Within the scholarly editing community, text has an understandably significant hegemony, but particularly in the case of digital editions, visuals are arguably as important as the text. What 'counts' as a digital edition increasingly has concerned scholarly editors. Indeed, Elena Pierazzo argues that only a combination of digital 'methods of production' and their research outputs can qualify a work as a *digital* edition (Pierazzo 2015). With the introduction of digital methods to the creation of scholarly editions, editors either have gained technical skills in user-interface and graphic design, collaborated with technical staff who take on these tasks, or a combination of the two. This adaptation to new methods and collaborations shows that it is possible to address issues that come up in a specifically digital work environment. It also indicates that it is possible to address the needs of diverse digital user groups with the creation of further audio-visual aids.

Film as documentation

One way of using film to document the digital edition is by creating a visual user-guide as an ancillary video for the edition. This could be as simple as a screencast showing a narrator clicking on different links in the edition, with a voice-over and subtitles explaining its mark-up style, or its modules, where to find the critical apparatus and how to download the XML files (to name just a few options). Films could be broken down into different competency levels or familiarity with digital editions, *e.g.* 'beginner', 'intermediate', and 'advanced'. Opportunities abound for creativity in this medium. Further, creating a user-guide is a good exercise for scholarly editors and others who work on digital editions to think through how their editions will be used and *how* to effectively communicate the options for use and reuse of data. Film is a medium well-suited to couple with traditional academic output like research papers, written user-guides and conference presentations about projects. Diverse user groups receive something that is visually demonstrative, but

also allows – through easy interfaces – for users to start, stop, pause, go back, repeat, increase or lower volume, increase or decrease window size, and perform other simple functions which customize the viewing experience.

Perceived Problems

One perceived problem is simply where to start if a scholarly editor has no experience in filmmaking. Luckily, there are many written guides and short films on how to make short films. There are also workshops (many of them free) and subscription-based websites and MOOCs which provide simple instruction on how to use equipment, how to storyboard and edit, and how to compress and code short films. Perhaps the greatest reason to choose this medium is that it is another opportunity to collaborate: many university and public libraries create short films about their online and in-house exhibits in order to gain public awareness. If they have an in-house production team, it is possible that the team can provide supplies, staff, and advice to a digital editing project. There is no one way to do this – film editing and output is similar to the TEI in that there are standards but they can be employed in different ways for different people and different audiences.

Another perceived problem is expense. Getting started with digital equipment can be overwhelming, and with the added cost of some top-of-the-line equipment, the cost-benefit analysis can immediately outweigh any desire to get started in this medium. Luckily the market for affordable video-capable DSLR cameras and lenses has expanded in the last ten years, and there is a growing market of refurbished equipment as well. There are also many companies (some that ship to several countries) which rent out digital equipment. And, if a project is connected to a library or university, that institution may have its own equipment that can be rented by university-affiliated employees. Most DSLR enthusiasts start out with borrowed or rented equipment to get a ‘feel’ for this medium, so cost can be kept relatively low for first-time users.

A third perceived problem is time. Film is its own form of storytelling, and, even in short videos this can require a lot of time and energy, resources which may be in short supply. Using collaborative networks and thinking carefully about how to construct a sufficient user-guide while the edition is being built is a good way to offset time cost, as the work of storyboarding can be done in parallel with the work of building the actual edition.

A fourth perceived problem is peer-review. Digital project collaborators already face significant concern about how to properly assess the scholarly merit of their work. Yet it is also possible that by opening up this work to include films, one opens up the possibility of constructive review and assessments from new media scholars, film studies scholars, and others who have expertise in visual storytelling. And this type of film is not seen as a replacement for scholarly output, but rather as a support of it. There is still space for ‘traditional’ peer-review in the form of the written work of the edition, and through well-respected avenues of publication and dissemination such as conferences, academic journals, and monographs.

Conclusion

Taking time to document our processes, particularly with regard to collaborative efforts, can arguably be described as a cornerstone of digital humanities research. The current system of project-based output in the digital humanities could benefit from diverse methods of visual storytelling to aid a diverse group of users. This may prove a challenge to scholarly editors without the benefit of significant training in filmmaking, but the cultural heritage sector has proven expertise in this medium, and as such is an area where collaborations can be made. The viral nature of digital video through social media sharing can benefit digital projects as a way of grabbing attention and broadening audience interaction. In order to sustain attention, digital academic films must be focused on effective digital storytelling, and on the users. There are lots of different types of short films – documentaries, trailers, interviews, videos – that explore the materiality of a specific text or time period covered in the edition, and explanations of methodology; all of which can provide interesting ancillary materials to digital editions.

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